

Primary in classes dictionary on work methodology .

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Abstract : In the article initial class students for created mother language and reading textbooks and in them there is words with connected without dictionary on work through the word wealth development methods and as well as recommendations giving passed .

Key words : Dictionary , word , reader , development , synonym words , connection , word activity , reading , education , writing .

Perfect a person adult in delivery initial education no doubt strong foundation role passes . As you know , the beginning class to his students education in giving important of duties main part reading in their classes done is increased . Mother language and reading in their classes take to go all of training leader place speech to grow being , he is literate teaching , beautiful to write skills formation and of students thinking scope expand such as tasks own into takes Students speech to grow , first of all , theirs dictionary enrichment with depends . Word wealth in raising dictionary on work big practical important have Under study the text on the surface dictionary work transfer in the process students of the tongue dictionary to the composition special was outdated words , new appear was words , profession about words , dialect special words , artistic to style special words with practical in terms of getting to know they go In our language there is was innumerable words in mind save staying and them in speech right and appropriate apply in getting of the tongue dictionary content certain layers or to groups separate learning ie outdated the word is new appear was word , profession about word , dialect special the word such as concepts The first theory about data with introduction very important is counted . To the students of the tongue dictionary content in teaching dictionary on work ways . Word of the tongue meaning means main is unity . Word and the word compound sure things , abstract concepts , feelings represents In the language there is has been all word and of phrases sum dictionary composition or lexicon is called Lexicology Uzbek of the language dictionary content who learns is a department . Lexicology dictionary contained of words in speech meaning to express feature , use activity , rich to go , some of words wear and tear out departure , meaning to move event such as learns . For this reason lexicology dictionary on work methodology linguistic basis is considered Har how speech statement grammar in terms of mutually linked to content suitable word and word of compounds known in consistency from placement is made . A person's dictionary how rich and developed if , his the speech will be so rich ; own his opinion sure and expressive statement to reach wide chance is created . Artistic works students dictionary and speech in enrichment the most believable source is considered Reading in their classes artistic works with acquaintance , analysis to do in the process students dictionary known topics is also rich in goes For example , year to the seasons about topics with get to know in the process in nature changes , birds , animals , animals world , trees , grasses with depends concepts if formed , spirituality , goodness and evil , friendship in topics works learning through human relations , manners on the surface certain to conclusions will come . Dictionary on work for special lesson not separated . He is all subjects in learning , mainly , mother language and reading in their classes textbook materials to teach with depends without take will go Mother language in their classes dictionary on work students speech to grow , literacy to form , word wealth to enrich , speech culture to upgrade focus because of this the

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work in schools it starts from the 1st grade and whole study in the process continue will be delivered .

At school speech of cultivation important of duties one dictionary on to work to improve , to arrange put , his main directions separate and students ' reasoning dictionary enrichment process manage is considered At school dictionary on work methodology four main direction in the eye holds :

1. Students ' dictionary enrichment , that is new words as well as children in the dictionary was some of words new meanings appropriation . Mother of the language dictionary wealth knowing get for student own to the dictionary each 8-10 new ones a day the word , that's it including mother language in their classes 4-6 words addition , i.e that's it words the meaning assimilation it is necessary 2. To the students ' dictionary accuracy input .This is own into the following takes :

a) student thorough did not master of words the meaning complete appropriation , i.e that's it words to the text input , meaning near to words comparison , antonym choose ways with their meaning accuracy input ;

b) speak sarcastic meaning , many meaningful words mastering ;

c) of words synonyms , synonyms of words meaning edges mastering ;

d) some phraseological of units the meaning appropriation .

3. Activation of the dictionary , ie students the meaning understanding , but own speech in welfare not using inactive in the dictionary the words active to the dictionary transfer Of this for that's it words in the presence of the word compound and sentences will be made , they those who studied again narration , conversation , statement and in the essay is used .

4. Literary in the language unused words students active from the dictionary inactive to the dictionary transfer Such to words of children speech environment under the influence of by itself the rest literary language to the norm not included , some literary work and conversation in the language applicable simple the word and phrases , dialect and social to the group about words enters Literary language norm said the concept After mastering , students above explained words instead of literary in the language from words use they start Students dictionary and speech in enrichment the most believable source artistic works is considered Uzbek language high artistic images using they absorb . Reading in class children dictionary known to topics about words he gets rich at the expense of it . They are to the dictionary moral concepts expressive cute , sweet , kind , brave , brave , brave , hardworking such as many words will be added . Text on work in the process a lot meaningful words , synonyms , portable in a sense usable words , some phraseological compounds knowing they get

Summary by doing so to speak initial class to his students lexicon knowledge to give only mother language lessons with limited without staying , reading lessons teaching during will go In general start class to his students of the tongue dictionary content by teaching to go their the word wealth increases , speech culture raises , national of our language great power , magic and charm felt full people to be growth provides .

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